

PERFORMANCE OF TEACHERS-IN-CHARGE AS SCHOOL HEAD AND CLASSROOM TEACHER IN THE THIRD CONGRESSIONAL DISTRICT OF QUEZON: BASIS FOR INTERVENTION

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ABSTRACT

The study focused on the performance of Teachers-In-Charge as School Heads and Classroom Teachers in the 3rd Congressional District of Quezon. The study employed the descriptive type of research utilizing (55) respondents with an adopted standardized performance evaluation instrument as the primary data gathering tool and a statistical tool as the results measuring and analysis device. The study revealed that typical respondents are described mainly as the ages 36 to 40, female-dominated, married, bachelor's degree holders, Teacher III in position, monograde classes handler, and TIC for 1-5 years. Moreover, the level of performance of the TIC as school head in terms of the Office Performance and Commitment Review based on the Results-Based Performance Management System – Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads has a very satisfactory rating. The level of performance of the TIC as a classroom teacher when measured based on KRAs of the Individual Performance and Commitment Review has also a very satisfactory rating. Despite the very satisfactory level of performance, the research findings revealed that TICs must improve their skills in the following areas: utilization of relevant research findings in leading strategically; assisting teachers in the review, contextualization, and implementation of learning standards; and, developing self and others, which serve as the basis for intervention.

Keywords: *Level of performance, Teachers-In-Charge, School Head, Classroom Teacher*

INTRODUCTION

The school is said to be the second home for all learners. Specifically, it is the venue for all the learnings of the schoolchildren substantial to their everyday lives. According to Republic Act No. 9155, Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001, "The school shall be the heart of the formal education system." Schools must have a single goal: to provide the greatest possible primary education for all students. According to Section 6.1, Rule VI of the Implementing Rules and Regulations of RA 9155, all public elementary and secondary schools, or a cluster thereof, must have a school head. A school head is defined under this act as "a person who is responsible for the administrative and instructional supervision of a school or cluster of schools." They serve as key leaders in the country's education system and are indispensable in achieving the government's aim of providing quality primary education. The primary functions of the school head, as defined in the act mentioned above, are administrative management and instructional leadership.

In the international scene, several authors from different research describe the functions and roles of the school head such as principal or any other equivalent position as the chief executive of schools who has multifarious tasks to accomplish for successful administration of the school system. Ezeocha (2000) views the roles of school head as supervision of instruction, curriculum development and evaluation, school-community relationship, staff-personnel administration, student personnel administration, management of school finance and school physical facilities. This further expounds the same extent of responsibilities given to teachers-in-charge who are designated to manage the schools without a principal.

In the Philippines, the preparation for being a full-time school head, such as a head teacher or principal, begins when a teacher becomes the teacher-in-charge of the school. Given, DepEd Order No. 85, series 2003, this states that the Schools Division Superintendent shall designate Teachers-In-Charge (TIC) in schools without principal items. A teacher-in-charge must have at least three (3) years of experience and undergo a screening process conducted by the Division Office. This was reiterated in DepEd Order No. 42, series 2007. Aside from being a classroom teacher, he or she performs the work being done by full-pledged school leaders. The current situation in the country tells us that TICs are regular teachers who serve the school with two different roles. This results in conflicts in their line of work as a classroom teacher and as a school administrator which affects both their performances.

DepEd Quezon is one of the largest divisions in Region IV-A that has many teachers-in-charge. There are four congressional districts, but they have only a few full-time school heads. Likewise, in this division, particularly in Macalelon District, out of eighteen (18) public elementary schools, fourteen (14) schools are being managed by teachers-in-charge. Most of them were in the Teacher I position. In previous years, they

were designated upon the recommendation of the school head before them and the district supervisor to the Schools Division Superintendent. At the present time, qualified teachers may apply for a TIC designation as needed. Further, they had no training as school leaders before they were designated as ones. There are different administrative and instructional supervision tasks given to them.

Role theory posits that different roles people perform and how expectations and interpretations of these roles affect people's experiences both at work and personally. A person may have competing responsibilities that take up their time, making it impossible for them to dedicate the same amount of time to activities in one role and activities in another (Greenhaus & Beutell, 1985). According to Lobel (1991), the utilitarian perspective on role investment contends that roles are compared to each other, resulting in a win-lose situation where time spent on one job reduces time spent on another. There are two ways that this could happen. First, it could be physically difficult to fulfill the demands of one function due to time constraints in another. Time constraints might sometimes lead to a preoccupation with one role while trying to fulfill the requirements of another role (Evans and Bartolome, 1979). In relation to the dual roles of the TICs, who has administrative and classroom teaching functions, this theory relates with the idea that TICs perform two different roles that might affect their performance in doing such. This may also give the context to look for its relationship because it is imperative to know what significance it may bring to make necessary intervention to improve their performances.

The researcher was motivated to conduct the study because of the problems encountered by the TICs in the locality concerning their functions as school heads and classroom teachers, which may affect their performance in doing such roles. The relationship between role overload and productivity at work stays little comprehended. Since work performance is the foundation of an organization's success, it has been established as the primary criterion for employee evaluation and reward. Understanding how and when role overload affects work performance is crucial for management scholars and practitioners. Boundary circumstances most certainly exist because the relationship between role overload and performance has been found to be beneficial in some research but negative in others (LePine et al., 2004; Gilboa et al., 2008; Bowling et al., 2015).

Research Questions

This study aims to determine the level of performance of teachers-in-charge as school heads and classroom teachers.

Specifically, it aims to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of performance of the teachers-in-charge as school heads based on the Office Performance and Commitment Review?
 - 1.1 Leading Strategically
 - 1.2 Managing School Operations and Resources
 - 1.3 Focusing on Teaching and Learning
 - 1.4 Developing Self and Others
 - 1.5 Building Connections
2. What is the level of performance of the teachers-in-charge as classroom teachers

based on the Individual Performance and Commitment Review?

2.1 Content Knowledge and Pedagogy

2.2 Learning Environment

2.3 Diversity of Learners, Curriculum and Planning, & Assessment and Reporting

2.4 Community Linkages and Professional Engagement, & Professional Growth and Professional Development

3. Is there a significant difference between the performance of TIC as school head and classroom teacher when group according to?

3.1 Teaching position

3.2 Type of school handled

4. Is there a significant relationship between the performance of TIC as school head and classroom teacher?

5. What intervention could be proposed based on the result of the study?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized a quantitative descriptive research design method. It suited to this type of research since it aimed to describe and determine the performance of TICs as school heads and classroom teachers and its relationship to their demographic profiles. A descriptive type of research aims to gather information, present conditions, and describe the nature of the situation. It was used to describe the characteristics of a population studied. It does not answer questions about how, when, and why the characteristics occurred (Wikipedia).

Research Locale

The study was conducted in the Third Congressional District of Quezon Province. This is one of the four congressional districts of Quezon, originally known as Tayabas, referred to as the Bondoc Peninsula. Since 1987, it has been represented in the House of Representatives. The municipalities that make up the district are Agdangan, Buenavista, Catanauan, General Luna, Macalelon, Mulanay, Padre Burgos, Pitogo, San Andres, San Francisco, San Narciso, and Unisan. These municipalities are located on the southern portion of the Tayabas Isthmus, and the southwest shore of the Ragay Gulf.

DepEd Quezon is one of the largest divisions in Region IV-A CALABARZON that has many teachers-in-charge. It is indeed important to help them to improve their performance as a school head and address the issues related to their roles as classroom teachers.

Since most of the school heads in the third congressional district were teachers designated as TICs, the researcher chose this locale to be her respondents. These school heads were ordinary classroom teachers that needed help in terms of performing two different roles.

Research Population and Sample

In choosing the population and sample, the researcher applied purposive sampling, where the researcher purposely selected the TICs as respondents of this study due to the challenges met in the locality when performing the tasks of a school head and a classroom teacher at the same time. The conduct of the study utilized a combination of in-person and online platform, so the internet access of the desired number of respondents was considered.

Table 1

List of Respondents in the Third Congressional District of Quezon

Municipality	School District	Total No. of Schools with TICs	Total No. of Respondents
Agdangan	Agdangan	3	3
Buena Vista	Buena Vista 1	3	3
	Buena Vista 2	4	3
Catanauan	Catanauan 1	4	3
	Catanauan 2	3	3
General Luna	General Luna	7	6
Macalelon	Macalelon	14	12
Mulanay	Mulanay 1	3	3
	Mulanay 2	3	2
Padre Burgos	Padre Burgos	4	3
Pitogo	Pitogo	4	3
San Andres	San Andres	4	3
San Francisco	San Francisco	4	3
San Narciso	San Narciso 1	4	3
	San Narciso 2	2	2
Unisan	Unisan	0	0
Total		66	55

Table 1 shows the study's population which was made up of TICs in the Third Congressional District in the Division of Quezon and computed with the statistician's help. The appropriate sample size, given the population size and specified combination of precision, confidence, and variability, is 55. (This represents the count or number of TICs in the selected district.)

Research Instrument

A survey questionnaire used a standardized performance evaluation tool to gather the necessary information. It was divided into three parts, with the *first* dealing with the

questions that determine the demographic profile of the respondents. The *second* part contained indicators that evaluated the performance of the school heads using the OPCR, initiated by the Division of Quezon. The *third* part contained indicators that determine their performance as classroom teachers based on the KRAs of their IPCR. The study's respondents were the TICs in the third congressional district of Quezon.

Since the study used standardized performance evaluation tools, validation was not a requirement. Pilot testing was done with several TICs outside the research locale to rehearse the research study and test the research approach with a few test participants before conducting the main study (Wright & So, 2022). The researcher prepared several letters addressed to the Division Superintendent and all district supervisors concerned to ask permission to conduct the study. A cover letter was prepared to inform respondents in the purpose of the questionnaire and to assure them that their responses would be treated with utmost confidentiality.

Data Gathering Procedure

Moreover, the researcher requests a letter to the Superintendent of the Schools Division of Quezon to approve the distribution of survey questionnaires to ensure the maximum cooperation of the target respondents. The distributions, and the retrieval, were personally conducted by the researcher using online forms and, or in-person methods. After the retrieval, the gathered data were generated by the statistician for statistical treatment and data analysis.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The data gathered through the questionnaire were classified, tabulated, and analyzed. The data that answered the specific problems were treated as follows: The scale below was used for the analysis of the data gathered.

Weight	Range Scale	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.51-5.00	Outstanding (O)
4	3.51-4.50	Very Satisfactory (VS)
3	2.51-3.50	Satisfactory (S)
2	1.51-2.50	Unsatisfactory (US)
1	1.00-1.50	Poor (P)

A mean score was used to determine the level of performance of TICs as school heads and classroom teachers.

Mean Score

$$M = \sum fw/n$$

Where:

M is the mean

f is the frequency

w is the weight

n is the number of cases

The Kruskal-Wallis H-Test was used to determine the significance of the difference.

One-Way ANOVA

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Degrees of Freedom	Mean Squares (MS)	F
Within	$SSW = \sum_{j=1}^k \sum_{i=1}^l (x - \bar{x}_j)^2$	$df_w = k - 1$	$MSW = \frac{SSW}{df_w}$	$F = \frac{MSB}{MSW}$
Between	$SSB = \sum_{j=1}^k (\bar{x}_j - \bar{x})^2$	$df_b = n - k$	$MSB = \frac{SSB}{df_b}$	
Total	$SST = \sum_{j=1}^n (x_j - \bar{x})^2$	$df_t = n - 1$		

$$\rho = 1 - \frac{U \Delta u}{n(n^2 - 1)}$$

To interpret the results of Spearman Rho Correlation, the following continuum was used:

Size of Correlation	Interpretation
±1.00	Perfectly positive/ negative correlation
±0.90 – 0.99	Very high positive/ negative correlation
±0.70 – 0.89	High positive/ negative correlation
±0.50 – 0.69	Moderately positive/ negative correlation
±0.30 – 0.49	Low positive/ negative correlation
±0.01 – 0.29	Negligible correlation
0.00	No correlation at all

RESULTS

Part I. Level of Performance of the TIC as School Head in terms of the Office Performance and Commitment Review Form based on the RPMS-PPSSH

Table 2

Mean Scores of the Level of Performance of the TIC as School Head using Office Performance and Commitment Review based on the RPMS-PPSSH for Leading Strategically

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Develop with the planning team school plans aligned with institutional goals and policies	4.24	Very Satisfactory
2. Implement programs in the school that support the development of learners	4.40	Very Satisfactory
3. Utilize available monitoring and evaluation processes and tools to promote learner achievement	4.18	Very Satisfactory
4. Utilize relevant research findings from reliable sources in facilitating data-driven and evidence-based innovations to improve school Performance	3.91	Very Satisfactory
5. Manage school data and information using technology, to ensure efficient and effective school operation	4.38	Very Satisfactory
Grand Mean:	4.22	Very Satisfactory

Legend: "Outstanding (4.51 – 5.00)", "Very Satisfactory (3.51 – 4.50)", "Satisfactory (2.51 – 3.50)", "Unsatisfactory (1.51 – 2.50)", "Poor (1.00 – 1.50)"

Table 3

Mean Scores of the Level of Performance of the TIC as School Head using Office Performance and Commitment Review Form based on the RPMS-PPSSH for Managing School Operations and Resources

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Manage school data and information using technology, to ensure efficient and effective school operation	4.29	Very Satisfactory
2. Exhibit efficient and effective practices in the management of finances consistently adhering to policies, guidelines and issuances in allocation, procurement, disbursement and liquidation aligned with the school plan.	4.31	Very Satisfactory
3. Establish shared accountability in managing school facilities and equipment in adherence to policies, guidelines and issuances on acquisition, recording, utilization, repair and maintenance, storage and disposal.	4.24	Very Satisfactory
4. Manage staffing such as teaching load distribution and grade level and subject area assignment in adherence to laws, policies, guidelines and issuances based on the needs of the school	4.25	Very Satisfactory
5. Manage school safety for disaster preparedness, mitigation and resiliency to ensure continuous delivery of instruction	4.31	Very Satisfactory
Grand Mean:	4.28	Very Satisfactory

Legend: "Outstanding (4.51 – 5.00)", "Very Satisfactory (3.51 – 4.50)", "Satisfactory (2.51 – 3.50)", "Unsatisfactory (1.51 – 2.50)", "Poor (1.00 – 1.50)"

Table 4

Mean Scores of the Level of Performance of the TIC as School using Office Performance and Commitment Review based on the RPMS-PPSSH for Focusing on Teaching and Learning

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Assist teachers in the review, contextualization, and implementation of learning standards to make the curriculum relevant for learners	3.98	Very Satisfactory
2. Provide technical assistance to teachers on teaching standards and pedagogies within and across curriculum areas to improve their teaching practice and ensure integration of career awareness and opportunities in the provision of learning experiences aligned with the curriculum.	4.02	Very Satisfactory
3. Use validated feedback obtained from learners, parents, and other stakeholders to help teachers improve their performance and implement learner discipline policies that are developed collaboratively with stakeholders including parents, school personnel and the community.	4.00	Very Satisfactory
4. Manage a learner-friendly inclusive and healthy learning environment and utilize learning outcomes in developing data-based interventions to maintain learner achievement and attain other performance indicators.	4.15	Very Satisfactory
5. Provide technical assistance to teachers in using learning assessment tools, strategies and results consistent with curriculum requirements to ensure accountability in achieving higher learning outcomes.	4.05	Very Satisfactory
Grand Mean:	4.04	Very Satisfactory

Legend: "Outstanding (4.51 – 5.00)", "Very Satisfactory (3.51 – 4.50)", "Satisfactory (2.51 – 3.50)", "Unsatisfactory (1.51 – 2.50)", "Poor (1.00 – 1.50)"

Table 5

Mean Scores of the Level of Performance of the TIC as School Head using Office Performance and Commitment Review Form based on the RPMS-PPSSH for Developing Self and Others

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Set personal and professional development goals based on self-assessment aligned with the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads	4.22	Very Satisfactory
2. Participate in professional networks to upgrade knowledge and skills and to enhance practice	4.25	Very Satisfactory
3. Implement professional development initiatives to enhance strengths and address performance gaps among school personnel	4.13	Very Satisfactory
4. Implement the performance management system with a team to support the career advancement of school personnel, and to improve office performance	4.00	Very Satisfactory
5. Implement a school rewards system to recognize and motivate learners, school personnel and other stakeholders for exemplary performance and/or continued support	4.15	Very Satisfactory
Grand Mean:	4.15	Very Satisfactory

Legend: "Outstanding (4.51 – 5.00)", "Very Satisfactory (3.51 – 4.50)", "Satisfactory (2.51 – 3.50)", "Unsatisfactory (1.51 – 2.50)", "Poor (1.00 – 1.50)"

Table 6

Mean Scores of the Level of Performance of the TIC as School Head using Office Performance and Commitment Review Form based on the RPMS-PPSSH for Building Connections

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Manage diverse relationships with authorities, colleagues, parents and other stakeholders to encourage an enabling and supportive environment for learners.	4.18	Very Satisfactory
2. Manage school organizations, such as learner organizations, faculty clubs and parent-teacher associations, in support of the attainment of institutional goals.	4.27	Very Satisfactory
3. Implement inclusive practices, such as gender sensitivity, physical and mental health awareness, and culture responsiveness, to foster awareness, acceptance and respect.	4.25	Very Satisfactory
4. Communicate effectively in speaking and in writing to teachers, learners, parents and other stakeholders, through positive use of communication platforms, to facilitate information sharing, collaboration and support.	4.25	Very Satisfactory
5. Establish partnerships with the community, such as parents, alumni, authorities, industries, and other stakeholders, to strengthen support for learner development, as well as school and community improvement.	4.25	Very Satisfactory
Grand Mean:	4.24	Very Satisfactory

Legend: "Outstanding (4.51 – 5.00)", "Very Satisfactory (3.51 – 4.50)", "Satisfactory (2.51 – 3.50)", "Unsatisfactory (1.51 – 2.50)", "Poor (1.00 – 1.50)"

Part II. Level of Performance of the TIC as Classroom Teacher based on KRAs of the Individual Performance and Commit Review Form

Table 7

Mean Scores of the Level of Performance of the TIC as Classroom Teacher based on KRAs of the Individual Performance and Commit Review Form in terms of Content Knowledge and Pedagogy

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Applied knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas.	4.11	Very Satisfactory
2. Used research-based knowledge and principles of teaching and learning to enhance professional practice.	4.31	Very Satisfactory
3. Displayed proficient use of Mother Tongue, Filipino, and English to facilitate teaching and learning.	4.40	Very Satisfactory
4. Used effective verbal and non-verbal classroom strategies to support learner understanding, participation, engagement, and achievement.	4.25	Very Satisfactory
Grand Mean:	4.27	Very Satisfactory

Legend: "Outstanding (4.51 – 5.00)", "Very Satisfactory (3.51 – 4.50)", "Satisfactory (2.51 – 3.50)", "Unsatisfactory (1.51 – 2.50)", "Poor (1.00 – 1.50)"

Table 8

Mean Scores of the Level of Performance of the TIC as Classroom Teacher based on KRAs of the Individual Performance and Commit Review Form in terms of Learning Environment

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Established safe and secure learning environments to enhance learning through the consistent implementation of policies, guidelines, and procedures.	4.58	Outstanding
2. Maintained learning environments that promote fairness, respect, and care to encourage learning.	4.58	Outstanding
3. Maintained learning environments that nurture and inspire learners to participate, cooperate and collaborate in continued learning.	4.38	Very Satisfactory
4. Applied a range of successful strategies that maintain learning environments to motivate learners to work productively by assuming responsibility for their own learning.	4.13	Very Satisfactory
Grand Mean:	4.42	Very Satisfactory

Legend: "Outstanding (4.51 – 5.00)", "Very Satisfactory (3.51 – 4.50)", "Satisfactory (2.51 – 3.50)", "Unsatisfactory (1.51 – 2.50)", "Poor (1.00 – 1.50)"

Table 9

Mean Scores of the Level of Performance of the TIC as Classroom Teacher based on KRAs of the Individual Performance and Commit Review Form for Diversity of Learners, Curriculum and Planning & Assessment and Reporting

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Designed, adapted, and implemented teaching strategies that are responsive to learners with disabilities, giftedness, and talents	4.24	Very Satisfactory
2. Adapted and used culturally-appropriate teaching strategies to address effectively the needs of learners from indigenous groups	4.22	Very Satisfactory
3. Adapted and implemented learning programs that ensure relevance and responsiveness to the needs of all learners.	4.25	Very Satisfactory
4. Utilized assessment data to inform the modification of teaching and learning practices and programs.	4.42	Very Satisfactory
Grand Mean:	4.28	Very Satisfactory

Legend: "Outstanding (4.51 – 5.00)", "Very Satisfactory (3.51 – 4.50)", "Satisfactory (2.51 – 3.50)", "Unsatisfactory (1.51 – 2.50)", "Poor (1.00 – 1.50)"

Table 10

Mean Scores of the Level of Performance of the TIC as Classroom Teacher based on KRAs of the Individual Performance and Commit Review Form in terms of Community Linkages and Professional Engagement & Personal Growth and Professional Development

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Maintained learning environments that are responsive to community contexts.	4.16	Very Satisfactory
2. Reviewed regularly personal teaching practice using existing laws and regulations that apply to the teaching profession, and the responsibilities specified in the Code of Ethics for Professional Teachers	4.11	Very Satisfactory
3. Complied with and implemented school policies and procedures to foster harmonious relationships with learners, parents, and other stakeholders	4.18	Very Satisfactory

4. Applied a personal philosophy of teaching that is learner-centered	4.16	Very Satisfactory
5. Adopted practices that uphold the dignity of teaching as a profession by exhibiting qualities such as caring attitude, respect, and integrity.	4.16	Very Satisfactory
6. Set professional development goals based on the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers	4.15	Very Satisfactory
Grand Mean:	4.15	Very Satisfactory

Legend: "Outstanding (4.51 – 5.00)", "Very Satisfactory (3.51 – 4.50)", "Satisfactory (2.51 – 3.50)", "Unsatisfactory (1.51 – 2.50)", "Poor (1.00 – 1.50)"

Part III. Test for Significant Difference Between the Performance of TIC as School Head and Classroom Teacher when grouped according to: Teaching Position and Type of School Handled

Table 11

Kruskal Wallis H-Test: Comparison Between the Performance of TIC as School Head when Grouped according to Teaching Position

Indicators	Teaching Position	Mean	K-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Leading Strategically	Teacher I	4.26	0.725	0.696	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Teacher II	4.15				
	Teacher III	4.25				
Managing School Operations and Resources	Teacher I	4.25	1.660	0.436	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Teacher II	4.35				
	Teacher III	4.30				
Focusing on Teaching and Learning	Teacher I	3.68	1.735	0.420	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Teacher II	3.66				
	Teacher III	4.18				
Developing Self and Others	Teacher I	4.13	0.273	0.873	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Teacher II	4.16				
	Teacher III	4.16				
Building Connections	Teacher I	4.21	0.316	0.854	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Teacher II	4.25				
	Teacher III	4.23				

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 12

Kruskal Wallis H-Test: Comparison Between the Performance of TIC as Classroom Teacher when Grouped according to Teaching Position

Indicators	Teaching Position	Mean	K-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Content Knowledge & Pedagogy	Teacher I	4.23	1.284	0.526	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Teacher II	4.22				
	Teacher III	4.30				
Learning Environment	Teacher I	4.65	0.877	0.645	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Teacher II	4.35				
	Teacher III	4.40				
Diversity of Learners,	Teacher I	4.32	4.099	0.129	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant

Curriculum and Planning & Assessment and Reporting	Teacher II	3.66				
	Teacher III	4.35				
Community Linkages and Professional Engagement & Personal Growth and Professional Development	Teacher I	4.01	2.233	0.327	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Teacher II	4.23				
	Teacher III	4.20				

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 13

Kruskal Wallis H-Test: Comparison Between the Performance of TIC as School Head when Grouped according to Type of School Handled

Indicators	Type of School Handled	Mean	K-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Leading Strategically	Multi Grade	4.19	0.300	0.584	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Mono Grade	4.21				
Managing School Operations and Resources	Multi Grade	4.27	0.104	0.747	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Mono Grade	4.26				
Focusing on Teaching and Learning	Multi Grade	3.98	0.192	0.661	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Mono Grade	4.07				
Developing Self and Others	Multi Grade	4.17	0.039	0.844	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Mono Grade	4.14				
Building Connections	Multi Grade	4.22	0.822	0.365	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Mono Grade	4.20				

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 14

Kruskal Wallis H-Test: Comparison Between the Performance of TIC as Classroom Teacher when Grouped according to Type of School Handled

Indicators	Type of School Handled	Mean	K-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Content Knowledge & Pedagogy	Multi Grade	4.22	8.241	.004	Reject Ho	Significant
	Mono Grade	4.31				
Learning Environment	Multi Grade	4.37	.586	.444	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Mono Grade	4.41				
Diversity of Learners, Curriculum and Planning &	Multi Grade	4.29	.254	.614	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant

Assessment and Reporting	Mono Grade	4.42				
Community Linkages and Professional Engagement & Personal Growth and Professional Development	Multi Grade	4.06	.703	.402	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 15

Spearman Rank: Significant Relationship Between the Performance of TIC as School Head and as Classroom Teacher in terms of Content Knowledge and Pedagogy

Content Knowledge and Pedagogy					
Indicators	Correlation Coefficient	Interpretation	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Leading Strategically	0.183	Weak Positive Correlation	0.182	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Managing School Operations and Resources	0.128	Weak Positive Correlation	0.351	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Focusing on Teaching and Learning	0.266	Weak Positive Correlation	0.050	Reject Ho	Significant
Developing Self and Others	0.211	Weak Positive Correlation	0.122	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Building Connections	-0.083	Weak Negative Correlation	0.548	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 16

Spearman Rank: Significant Relationship Between the Performance of TIC as School Head and as Classroom Teacher in terms of Learning Environment

Learning Environment					
Indicators	Correlation Coefficient	Interpretation	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Leading Strategically	0.056	Weak Positive Correlation	0.686	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Managing School Operations and Resources	0.077	Weak Positive Correlation	0.578	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Focusing on Teaching and Learning	0.025	Weak Positive Correlation	0.854	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Developing Self and Others	-0.025	Weak Negative Correlation	0.854	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Building Connections	-0.019	Weak Negative Correlation	0.890	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 17

Spearman Rank: Significant Relationship Between the Performance of TIC as School Head and as Classroom Teacher in terms of Diversity of Learners, Curriculum and Planning & Assessment and Reporting

Diversity of Learners, Curriculum and Planning & Assessment and Reporting					
Indicators	Correlation Coefficient	Interpretation	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Leading Strategically	0.003	Weak Positive Correlation	0.985	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Managing School Operations and Resources	-0.102	Weak Negative Correlation	0.458	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Focusing on Teaching and Learning	-0.038	Weak Negative Correlation	0.782	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Developing Self and Others	0.021	Weak Positive Correlation	0.878	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Building Connections	-0.088	Weak Negative Correlation	0.523	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 18

Spearman Rank: Significant Relationship Between the Performance of TIC as School Head and as Classroom Teacher in terms of Community Linkages and Professional Engagement & Personal Growth and Professional Development

Community Linkages and Professional Engagement & Personal Growth and Professional Development					
Indicators	Correlation Coefficient	Interpretation	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Leading Strategically	0.686	Strong Positive Correlation	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Managing School Operations and Resources	0.717	Strong Positive Correlation	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Focusing on Teaching and Learning	0.800	Very Strong Positive Correlation	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Developing Self and Others	0.616	Strong Positive Correlation	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Building Connections	0.686	Strong Positive Correlation	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

DISCUSSION

Table 2 shows the mean scores of the level of performance of the TIC as school head using Office Performance and Commitment Review based on the RPMS-PPSSH for Leading Strategically. The grand mean was 4.22 with a verbal interpretation of "Very

Satisfactory." This implied that the level of performance of the TIC as school head has a very satisfactory rating in terms of the OPCR anchored to the PPSSH.

The top scorer showed that "the respondents implement programs in the school that support the development of learners", with a mean of 4.40. The data showed that even though the findings revealed that TICs are very satisfactory in leading strategically, they are still lacking in some of what they are expected to perform as a school head. Implementing programs in the school that support the development of the learners is one of the significant roles of the teacher-in-charge to fulfill as a school leader. The result implies that the respondents' level of performance pertaining to the indicators mentioned above is parallel with Muring (2014), which according to him, the school heads hold the position of leadership and are accountable for overseeing the creation and execution of all educational programs and initiatives inside the school.

The bottom scorer stated that "the respondents facilitate data-driven and evidence-based innovations to enhance school performance by utilizing pertinent research findings from dependable sources." This entails the respondents' performance in the conduct of action research in their schools is a bit lower in terms of means, which tells that TICs has a lot more rooms for improvement when it comes to facilitating data-driven and evidence-based innovations. As school leaders, they must seek to ensure that teachers' instructional content and techniques are informed by relevant research and demonstrated experiences. Utilization of credible research findings in promoting data-driven and evidence-based solutions to improve school performance is one of the things that support how school heads are leading strategically. One way a school administrator can address the challenges that education faces today is through the knowledge and application of action research. Sagor (2000) believes that leaders who engage in action research find the process to be an empowering experience. He states that relevance is guaranteed because the research focus was determined by the researcher, who utilizes the findings to enhance professional practice. TICs has displayed little engagement in terms of doing relevant research in the pursuit of enhanced school performance. This conforms with the article of Lundqvist & Westerlund (2022), which cited that research has found that delivering research-based education poses great challenges for school leaders, as well as revealing substantial variations in engagement in practice (Bryan & Burstow, 2017; Cochran-Smith & Lytle, 2009; Schenke, 2015; Schenke et al., 2016).

In contrast, TICs also utilize their knowledge and comprehension of the advancements in education policy and changes in schooling, social dynamics, and environmental trends to enhance educational opportunities within the school. They also possess up-to-date knowledge and comprehension of research about teaching, learning, and child development. They know how to apply this research to meet the needs of students within the school. This encompasses overseeing performance management in the school and implementing strategies to enhance teaching methods (AITSL, 2019).

In addition, these findings agreed to Day et al. (2020), which found that principals used data, research, inspection evidence, and observation as tools to enhance teaching and learning and thus to support school improvement. Also, for teachers-in-charge who

assumed office as full-pledged school heads, effective leaders of the school should be able to improve school vision and make changes in educational programs with a strong understanding of school reform (Martineau, 2012).

Table 3 shows the mean scores of the level of performance of the TIC as school head using the Office Performance and Commitment Review Form based on the RPMS-PPSSH for Managing School Operations and Resources. The grand mean was 4.28 with a verbal interpretation of "Very Satisfactory." The result implied that the level of performance of the TIC as school head in terms of the Office Performance and Commitment Review Form based on the RPMS–PPSSH, has a very satisfactory rating.

The highest rater indicated that "the respondents demonstrate efficient and successful financial management procedures, consistently adhering to announcements, policies, and guidelines for allocation, purchase, payment, and liquidation in line with the school plan," and "the responders manage school safety to ensure ongoing instruction delivery by preparing for, mitigating, and building resilience to disasters," with the same mean of 4.31. In these areas, TICs manifested well performance when it comes to management of resources and planning for the school's safety. This conforms in the previous studies which indicate that all the given competencies in managing school operations and resources have a significant relationship between school leaders' management competencies and school performance in terms of quality and efficiency (Valenzuela & Buenvenida, 2021). It was also found that in their study, school heads are very knowledgeable and skilled in financial management in terms of knowledge, adherence to guidelines, policies, and issuances, ensuring that funding allocation and procurement were coordinated with the school plan, which is required for efficient and effective school operations.

These findings are parallel to the national standards of excellence for headteachers in England which state that school leaders prioritize and allocate financial resources appropriately, ensuring efficiency, effectiveness, and integrity of public funds (Department for Education, UK, 2020).

The TICs also serve as the school's DRRM coordinator. They lead the school in the planning and management of school safety among others. Appointing an alternate among other school personnel to assist in implementing DRRM is hereby permitted. To maintain ongoing delivery of teaching, and manage school safety for disaster preparedness, mitigation, and resiliency. DepEd Order No. 21, s. 2015 stipulated the roles and responsibilities of school heads to establish a safety culture in the school.

The lowest rater showed that "the respondents establish shared accountability in managing school facilities and equipment in adherence to policies, guidelines, and issuances on the acquisition, recording, utilization, repair and maintenance, storage, and disposal," with a mean of 4.24. As the head of the school, TICs responsible for the management of school facilities. In this regard, the results are in relation to Day et. al (2020), which revealed that the school administrators recognized the importance of enhancing the learning environment and maximizing the effectiveness of teaching. They devised plans to upgrade the school infrastructure and facilities. Through improvements

in classrooms and overall school facilities they acknowledged the correlation between conditions for teaching and learning as well as the overall well-being and success of both teachers and students.

Also, principals work with others to produce and implement clear, evidence-based improvement plans and policies for the development of the school and its facilities. They recognize that a crucial part of the role is to lead and manage innovation and change to ensure the vision and strategic plan is put into action across the school and that its goals and intentions are realized (AITSL, 2019).

The results are related to the literature from Mpondo (2005), who claimed that the vital function of heads of schools is to secure and operate effective allocation, monitor, and control the use of resources. A school head is expected to prepare the school budget that covers different responsible areas for fulfilling education objectives, specifically teaching and learning processes.

Moreover, on the job performance of school heads, Regala (2020) found that school heads have exhibited commendable job performance that encourages and inspires the teachers to cooperate with their school heads to achieve the goals and objectives of the school. The result explains that school heads were very good at performing their duties and responsibilities efficiently, including submitting progress reports to the Division Superintendent of Schools, implementing the project and MOOE program of the school, holding faculty meetings at the appropriate time, directing and guiding the teachers to accomplish assigned work, supervising and managing the teachers using their hearts, heads, and hands, making a program plan for faculty development, and preparing a budget for physical facilities.

Table 4 shows the mean scores of the level of performance of the TIC as school head using Office Performance and Commitment Review Form based on the RPMS-PPSSH for focusing on teaching and learning. The grand mean was 4.04 with a verbal interpretation of "Very Satisfactory." The result implied that the level of performance of the TIC as school head in terms of the Office Performance and Commitment Review Form, based on the RPMS–PPSSH, has a very satisfactory rating.

The highest indicator elicited that "the respondents maintain learner achievement and meet other performance indicators by creating a learner-friendly, inclusive, and healthy learning environment, as well as use learning outcomes to inform the development of data-driven interventions," with a mean of 4.15.

The result indicated that the respondents have time for school supervision in the school to promote the vision and mission of the school. As cited in the work of Valenzuela and Buenvenida (2021), contrary to the work of Ampofo et al. (2019), they found that school heads devote very little time to supervision, especially in lesson planning and the delivery of learning by teachers. The study was able to establish that instructional supervision has a significant influence on teachers' performance. As a result of this, the

study recommends that the school heads perform direct supervision as well as a reduction in the teaching load of the heads of departments.

Successful educational leaders foster a school community that's inclusive nurturing and supportive with a focus on promoting the academic achievement and overall well-being of every student (NPBEA, 2015).

The lowest indicator stated that "the respondents help teachers create a curriculum that is meaningful for students by reviewing, contextualizing, and implementing learning standards," with a mean of 3.98.

The role of the school head to effectively manage the LAC organization and ensure the hosting of LAC sessions that it is important for school leaders to take turns supporting teachers, in reviewing adapting and implementing learning standards to make the curriculum more meaningful, for students. As stated in this directive, curriculum contextualization involves aligning the curriculum content and instructional approaches to better meet the needs of learners, which teachers should also consider. (D.O. 36, s. 2015) The result also showed that the respondents assisted teachers in the technicalities of school administration. The study of Lashway (2009) supported such a claim, who opines that principals today should likewise serve as pioneers for students learning. They should know the program's content and pedagogical procedures. They should know, collect, and analyze data in a way that fuels excellence. As an instructional leader, the school head creates a school environment conducive to learning and becomes accountable for learning outcomes. The main components of an efficient and effective instructional system are to diagnose or set targets, plan, modify, or improve instruction, teach, assess (formatively), modify or improve instruction, assess (summative), and report to stakeholders (RA 9155, 2001).

Table 5 shows the mean scores of the level of performance of the TIC as school head in terms of their Office Performance and Commitment Review Form based on the RPMS-PPSSH for Developing Self and Others. The grand mean was 4.15, with a verbal interpretation of "very satisfactory." The result implied that the level of performance of the TIC as school head in terms of the Office Performance and Commitment Review Form, based on the RPMS–PPSSH, has a very satisfactory rating.

The top indicator stated that "the respondents engage in professional networks to improve practice and advance knowledge and skills.," with a mean of 4.25. The result entails understanding laws, policies, guidelines, and issuances in the school. In contrast to the study of Valenzuela & Buenvenida (2021), they found out that, school administrators nonetheless try to assist and encourage their staff members' aspirations to better themselves, even though they are less able to demonstrate and apply their knowledge of laws, policies, guidelines, and issuances.

Moreover, D.O. 36, s. 2015 states the role of the school head to effectively manage the Learning Action Cell organization and ensure the hosting of LAC sessions that it is important for school leaders to take turns supporting teachers, in reviewing adapting and

implementing learning standards to make the curriculum more meaningful, for students. This also confirms participation in professional networks to upgrade one's knowledge and skills as well as enhancement of practice.

Similarly, school heads must utilize learning outcomes in the development of data-based interventions to maintain learner achievement and attain other performance indicators. Learning Action Cell could reach an agreement to investigate initiatives and meet the stated need. Interventions may take the shape of learning resources, instructional materials, equipment, facilities, or teaching styles, modes of teaching, programs, and others.

The bottom indicator stated that "the respondents assist school staff in advancing their careers and enhancing office performance by implementing the performance management system with a team," with a mean of 4.00.

According to Day et. al (2020), the five key Professional Practices which are specified, through which the Leadership Requirements includes managing performance, effective continuing professional learning, and feedback.

Alar's 2016 study (as cited in Cañete, 2020) disclosed that whatever the school's image, it reflects on the administrators' performance. So, the lower the performance of the school heads, the lower the impact on the school.

The Department of Education issued DepEd Order No. 2, Series 2015, these are guidelines on the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS) establishment and implementation in the Department of Education. Its goal is to provide detailed instructions for implementing the Civil Service Commission's (CSC) Strategic Performance Management System (SPMS) in DepEd. These guidelines stipulate the specific mechanisms, criteria, and processes for the performance target setting, monitoring, evaluation, and development planning for schools and offices, covering all officials and employees, school-based and non-school-based, in the Department holding regular plantilla positions.

For the department order mentioned above, the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) is vigorously implemented. As defined in this mandate, it is a form that should reflect the individual commitments and performance of personnel covered by these regulations, such as teachers and master teachers. It must be accomplished by the individual personnel to reflect the agreed-upon individual key result areas (KRAs), objectives, and performance indicators. DepEd released DepEd Memorandum No. 004, s. 2022 or the Implementation of the Results-Based Performance Management System—Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers for School Year 2021–2022. This memorandum provides guidelines for the performance management and appraisal of teachers using the remaining 18 indicators in their RPMS, chosen as objectives for this school year. Creation of two kinds of objectives was constructed for regular teachers, such as classroom-observable and non-classroom-observable objectives. There are nine (9) classroom observable objectives for proficient teachers and

seven (7) for highly proficient teachers, whose performance indicators were identified as quality indicators. A total of thirteen (13) non-classroom observable objectives for both proficient and highly proficient teachers were made.

The evaluation of teacher work performance has served a variety of goals in recent years, one of which is to pinpoint areas of instruction deficiency and devise solutions. Because of this, gathering data that will be helpful in creating strategies that will improve instruction should be one of the objectives of assessing instructors' job performance. (Iwuagwu et al., 2016).

Furthermore, D.O. No. 42, s. 2017, aims to " use a standard measurement to evaluate teacher effectiveness, pinpoint areas of need, and offer assistance with professional development." The development of the Classroom Observation Tool (COT), based on the PPST's developmental framework, helps DepEd's initiative to provide a single tool to measure teachers' classroom performance. In this account, one of the primary means of verification (MOV) during the accomplishment of the IPCRF is the Classroom Observation Tool (D.M. No. 004, s. 2022).

On the other hand, The Office Performance Commitment and Review Form (OPCRF) is a form that is to be completed by the head of an office to represent the office's commitments and performance. The office KRAs, objectives, and performance indicators are reflected in this form. The OPCRf is equal to the IPCRF of the office's head. DepEd Quezon issued Division Memorandum No. 478, Series 2022, about the conduct of the year-end performance management review and the submission of the OPCRf for school- Table 6 shows the mean scores of the level of performance of the TIC as school head in terms of their Office Performance and Commitment Review Form based on the RPMS-PPSSH for Building Connections. The grand mean was 4.24 with a verbal interpretation of "Very Satisfactory." The result implied that the level of performance of the TIC as school head in terms of the Office Performance and Commitment Review Form, based on the RPMS–PPSSH, has a very satisfactory rating.

The highest rater elicited that "the respondents oversee educational groups including parent-teacher associations, faculty clubs, and learner organizations to help the institution achieve its objectives", with a mean of 4.27.

The results generated are about the findings in the study of Cañete (2020). Community partnership is very significant in sustaining the needs of the school in academics and extra-curricular activities. Such claim supports the study of Carpio (2014) entitled "Stakeholders Participation and School Improvement", where he emphasized the importance of communication while getting the best and appropriate partners in school improvement. Thus, if it happens, the school will likely have a significant improvement. The lowest rater stated that "the respondents maintain a variety of relationships with parents, teachers, coworkers, and other stakeholders to promote a welcoming and encouraging atmosphere for students", with a mean of 4.18. These findings also agree with the study of Day et al (2020), states the five essential professional practices through which leadership requirements enact that include developing and maintaining positive

partnerships with students, families and carers and the wider school community. Building and maintaining excellent relationships with staff members at all levels allowed school leaders to make them feel important and engaged. They showed concern for the workers' personal and professional welfare. Trust and mutual respect were evident in the connection between senior leadership teams (SLTs) and school leaders. Achieving long-term success was viewed as dependent on enhancing the school's reputation and interacting with the community. Together with their SLTs, school administrators cultivated strong ties with local authorities and established a network of connections between the school and other institutions and people. It was believed that the school would benefit from having close ties to important local stakeholders.

The result concurs with that of Motowidlo (2012), who found that job training offers an excellent opportunity to school heads since it reinforces knowledge and skills in supervising and managing the teachers and the school organization. Job training enables school heads to be more creative in making the program's action plan.

Part II. Level of Performance of the TIC as Classroom Teacher based on KRAs of the Individual Performance and Commit Review Form

Table 7 shows the mean scores about the level of performance of the TIC as a classroom teacher based on KRAs of the Individual Performance and Commitment Review Form for Content Knowledge and Pedagogy. The grand mean was 4.27 with a verbal interpretation of "Very Satisfactory." The result implied that the level of performance of the TIC as a classroom teacher, based on KRAs in terms of the Individual Performance and Commitment Review, has a very satisfactory rating.

The highest indicator exemplified that "the respondents displayed proficient use of Mother Tongue, Filipino, and English to facilitate teaching and learning" with a mean rating of 4.40. This elucidated that the curriculum may be contextualized to the language and culture of the learners. This explained how the curriculum could be tailored to the language and cultural preferences of the learners. In addition, curriculum contextualization refers to the process of aligning curriculum content with learner-relevant instructional strategies, which teachers should also consider. In this account, the TICs showed that they are reliable when it comes to the usage of language in the teaching-learning process.

The lowest indicator stated that "the respondents applied knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas" with a mean of 4.11. This indicated that the respondents may give mastery to the content knowledge within and across curriculum areas regardless of what subject matter they are teaching. This acknowledges how crucial it is for educators to have a solid grasp of the theories and concepts of teaching and learning, as well as how those ideas relate to one another and to other curriculum areas. Teachers' capacity to implement relevant and developmentally appropriate teaching based on current research and subject matter expertise is included in this context.

Table 8 shows the mean scores about the level of performance of the TIC as a classroom teacher based on KRAs of the Individual Performance and Commit Review Form for learning environment. The grand mean was 4.42 with a verbal interpretation of "Very Satisfactory". The result implied that the level of performance of the TIC as a classroom teacher, based on KRAs in terms of the Individual Performance and Commitment Review Form, has a very satisfactory rating.

The highest rater stated that "the respondents may establish safe and secure learning environments to enhance learning through the consistent implementation of policies, guidelines, and procedures" and "the respondents maintained learning environments that promote fairness, respect, and care to encourage learning" with the same means of 4.58. Its findings go counter to the PPST's, which indicates that respondents may guarantee a secure and comfortable learning environment for students. It emphasizes how important it is for educators to create safe, secure, equitable, and encouraging learning environments to encourage student responsibility and success. The domain focuses on setting up an atmosphere that is learning-focused and allows teachers to effectively control student conduct both in real and virtual spaces. It also emphasizes how important it is for teachers to make use of a variety of tools and offer mentally demanding and engaging exercises to foster positive classroom interactions that lead to the achievement of high learning standards. The lowest rater elicited that "the respondents applied a range of successful strategies that maintain learning environments to motivate learners to work productively by assuming responsibility for their own learning" with a mean of 4.39.

Table 9 shows the mean scores on the level of performance of the TIC as a classroom teacher based on the KRAs in the Individual Performance and Commit Review for Diversity of Learners, Curriculum, and Planning and Assessment and Reporting. The grand mean was 4.28 with a verbal interpretation of "Very Satisfactory". Commitment Review at the level of performance of the TIC as a classroom teacher, based on KRAs in the Individual Performance and Commitment Review, has a very satisfactory rating.

The top scorer indicated that "the respondents utilized assessment data to inform the modification of teaching and learning practices and programs" with a mean of 4.42. This demonstrated how educators and school administrators use learner-centered assessment to guarantee high-quality learning results. Additionally, all teachers must to be familiar with how to carry out the learner-centered assessment rules for the K–12 curriculum. Teachers and students receive the essential input regarding learning outcomes through assessment. Teachers can consistently choose, arrange, and employ sound assessment procedures with the help of this feedback, which also informs the reporting cycle (D.O. 35, s. 2016).

The bottom scorer showed that, "the respondents may adapt and use culturally-appropriate teaching strategies to address effectively the needs of learners from indigenous groups", with a mean of 4.22. This would suggest that during the teaching-learning process, lessons could be tailored to the cultural background of the students. Lesson planning is an essential part of a productive teaching and learning process since

it gives the teacher a clear structure for instruction and helps the class run more smoothly. It functions as a teacher's road map for what the students should learn and how it will be accomplished in the classroom. (Sehweil, 2022).

Table 10 shows the mean scores of the level of performance of the TIC as a classroom teacher based on KRAs in terms of the Individual Performance and Commitment Review in terms of Community Linkages and Professional Engagement and Personal Growth and Professional Development. The grand mean was 4.15 with a verbal interpretation of "Very Satisfactory." This implied that the level of performance of the TIC as a classroom teacher, based on KRAs of the Individual Performance and Commitment Review, has a very satisfactory rating.

The highest indicator stated that "the respondents obeyed and carried out the rules and regulations of the school to promote good relations with students, parents, and other stakeholders," with a mean of 4.18. This suggested that the responders get along well with the various school stakeholders. This necessitates community engagement in educational settings. It emphasizes the part teachers play in building ties between the school and the community to enhance the learning environment and the community's involvement in the educational process. It is required of teachers in this area to identify and seize opportunities that link classroom education to the interests, aspirations, and experiences of other important stakeholders as well as the greater school community. It has to do with how important it is for teachers to understand and fulfill their obligations to uphold professional ethics, responsibility, and transparency to promote constructive and friendly relationships with students, parents, schools, and the greater school community.

In addition, it agrees with AITSL (2022) which states that teachers welcome opportunities to engage with their school communities both within and outside of the classroom to enhance the educational experience for learners. They understand the significance of relationships between the community, the family, and the classroom for students' intellectual and social development.

Part III. Test for Significant Difference Between the Performance of TIC as School Head and Classroom Teacher when grouped according to: Teaching Position and Type of School Handled

Table 11 shows the Kruskal Wallis H-Test of the comparison between the performance of TIC as school head when grouped according to teaching position which is not statistically significant ($p = 0.696, 0.436, 0.420, 0.873, 0.854, > 0.05$). These findings illustrate that the responses do not differ when grouped according to teaching position.

The results revealed that no matter what position they are in, they can still perform their duties very satisfactorily. This means that TICs having Teacher I Position can perform the way Teacher II and Teacher III do. Contrasting to the study of Sarabia and Collantes (2020), teaching position was found to be a positive predictor of teaching

performance, meaning that teachers with higher positions were probably going to do better in the classroom. In addition, TICs are still capable of carrying out their responsibilities admirably despite the variations in teaching positions.

Table 12 shows the Kruskal Wallis H-Test of the comparison between the performance of TIC as classroom teacher when grouped according to teaching position which is not statistically significant ($p = 0.526, 0.645, 0.129, 0.327 > 0.05$). These findings demonstrate that there is no variation in the responses when they are categorized based on teaching position. The result is consistent with the study of Sumanga et al. (2022) which found to be insignificant in teaching performance as far as teaching position is concerned.

Table 13 shows the Kruskal Wallis H-Test of the comparison between the performance of TIC as school head when grouped according to type of school handled which is significantly not different ($p = 0.584, 0.747, 0.661, 0.844, 0.365 > 0.05$). TICs perform well regardless of the type of school handled. Handling multigrade and monograde school provides a wide range of duties. In addition to shaping the vision and guaranteeing the academic success of every learner, TICs also cultivate leadership in both learners and faculty, supervises daily operations, prepares programs in accordance with the needs of the school, and fosters an environment that is conducive to learning. This implies that both type of schools does not differ when it comes to performing their roles as school head in terms of the PPSSH (D.O. 24, s. 2020).

Table 14 shows the Kruskal Wallis H-Test of the comparison between the performance of TIC as classroom teacher when grouped according to type of school handled which found to be significantly different ($p = .004 < 0.05$) and not significantly different ($p = .444, .614, .402 > 0.05$). Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. There is no significant difference between the performance of TIC as classroom teachers when grouped according to the type of school handled. The results showed that, in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy, teachers teaching multi-grade classes outperform teachers teaching mono-grade classes since they are more involved in a variety of learning areas that span diverse grade levels.

Part IV. Test for Significant Relationship Between the Performance of TIC as School Head and as Classroom Teacher

Table 15 shows the Spearman Rank on the significant relationship between the Performance of TIC as School Head and as Classroom Teacher in terms of Content Knowledge and Pedagogy and Focusing on Teaching and Learning which found to be significant ($p = 0.182 > 0.05$). The rest of the indicators revealed the following result ($p = 0.122, 0.183, 0.050 \geq 0.05$). Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. There is no significant relationship between the performance of TIC as School Head and as Classroom Teacher. Based on the findings, being a school head has nothing to do with the teaching-learning process. Role overload is a factor in this circumstance. Administrative tasks occupy the time spent as a classroom teacher. In contrast, as to RA

9155, a school head is person who is responsible for the administrative and instructional supervision of a school or cluster of schools. In addition, as an instructional leader, a school head is responsible for what goes on inside the classroom and how the instructional time was utilized to make the teaching-learning process meaningful. Leadership and instructional supervision should meet the expectation that the school head and the teachers are open to suggestions and recommendations to improve classroom instruction for better learning outcomes. This rather crucial responsibility needs a broad understanding and know-how of the nitty-gritty of supervision so that a higher quality of learning is achieved (D.O. 85, s. 2003).

Table 16 shows the Spearman Rank on the significant relationship between the Performance of TIC as School Head and as Classroom Teacher in terms of Learning Environment ($p = 0.686, 0.578, 0.854, 0.854, 0.890 > 0.05$) which found to be not significant. Performing the role as a school head does not affect the learning environment. This demonstrates that TICs are exempt from having to consider how their decisions as school administrators may affect the learning environment.

Table 17 shows the Spearman Rank of the significant relationship between the Performance of TIC as School Head and as Classroom Teacher in terms of Diversity of Learners, Curriculum and Planning and Assessment and Reporting. In terms of Leading Strategically ($p = 0.985, 0.458, 0.782, 0.878, 0.523 > 0.05$) which is more than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted. There is no significant relationship between the performance of TIC as School Head and as Classroom Teacher in terms of diversity of learners, curriculum and planning, and assessment and reporting. According to Taylor (2023), Parkinson's Law emphasizes how time constraints, and a sense of urgency can enhance productivity. Individuals can consciously decrease their deadlines, improve their concentration, efficiency, and productivity, and complete tasks more quickly. More so, the findings show that good time management can lead to the attainment of a certain task without compromising other duties.

Table 18 shows the Spearman Rank on the significant relationship between the Performance of TIC as School Head and as Classroom Teacher in terms of Community Linkages and Professional Engagement and Personal Growth and Professional Development which has a significant relationship ($p = 0.000 < 0.05$) in all areas. These results state that in as much as the TICs performs higher in her role as a school head, his/her performance in community linkages professional engagement and personal growth and professional development gives a positive effect on her as a teacher.

Part V. Proposed Intervention

In response to the result of the study on Performance of Teachers-In-Charge as School Head and Classroom Teachers in the Third Congressional District of Quezon: Basis for Intervention, the conceptualization of PROJECT SIBAY SYSTEM for TICs was made possible. It stands for Strong Initiative to Build Assistance Yielding System for TICs. The scope of the intervention aims to address the level of performance of a TIC as School Head and as Classroom Teacher. This also addresses the variances of the responses on

the performance as School Head and Classroom Teacher with the degree of relationship to one another. The focus of the proposed intervention is mainly on creating activities on the areas with identified lower rating of performances leaning towards satisfactory level (3.51-4.00) that will support the teachers who are designated as TICs.

The intervention aims to provide activities that will help enhance the TIC's capabilities in the following areas: (a) utilization of relevant research findings in leading strategically; (b) assisting teachers in the review, contextualization, and implementation of learning standards; and (c) Developing self and others. The program design comprises a timeline that guides the implementation of various activities at the district or division level. Following implementation, the intervention's effectiveness will be assessed by monitoring and evaluation.

Conclusions

Based on the findings derived, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The level of performance of the TIC as school head based on the Office Performance and Commitment Review has a very satisfactory rating.
2. The level of performance of the TIC as a classroom teacher based on the Individual Performance and Commitment Review has a very satisfactory level.
3. There is no significant difference in all KRAs of the performance of TIC as a School Head and Classroom Teacher when grouped according to teaching position and the type of school handled. Hence, the research hypothesis is accepted.
4. There is significant relationship and no significant relationship in some KRAs of the performance of TIC as a School Head and Classroom Teacher. Hence, the research hypothesis is partially accepted and partially rejected.
5. The researcher proposed an intervention program on the areas with identified lower rating of performances leaning towards satisfactory level.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions drawn, the following were recommended:

1. Teachers-in-Charge manifested very satisfactory level on their performance as they have shown good performance of their roles but on the other hand, this does not mean that they have achieved the standards set by the Department that are expected of them. There were few performance indicators which need to be improved to better perform their roles as school leader. They still need to strive to meet the prescribed standards by attending trainings related to PPSSH domains most specially those who are new in this designation/position.
2. TICs as a classroom teacher also displayed a very satisfactory rating on their performance while some indicators still need to be improved to achieve higher level of performance. More so, in line with the Role Theory, TICs might encounter challenges due to the dual functions they are dealing with every day. In this account, it is recommended that higher authorities may consider looking

- for the necessary actions that will readily give assistance to the TICs' undertaking pertaining to their performance as classroom teacher specifically the number of teaching loads given to them to improve their performance mentioned above and to give an order of priority to their tasks.
3. As far as the results indicate, there is no significant difference in all the performance indicators of TIC as a School Head and Classroom Teacher when grouped according to teaching position and type of school handled, however, the TICs may be given the opportunity to obtain at least higher school head position to augment the time focusing on the administrative tasks and lessen the actual class encounter. In this way, He will be able to manage the two duties more skillfully and fulfill his duty as head of the school more effectively.
 4. As the findings suggest, there is a significant relationship between the Performance of TIC as School Head and as Classroom Teacher when talking about Content Knowledge and Pedagogy and Focusing on Teaching and Learning. TICs may attend trainings focusing on the pedagogical approaches in teaching as well as relevant educational engagements in Focusing on Teaching and Learning to capacitate School Heads. Moreover, reduced the number of actual class encounters to alleviate the teaching loads of the TICs.
 5. The proposed intervention program of this study may be used by the recipient teachers who are designated as teacher-in-charge in the Division of Quezon to improve their performance in the areas with identified lower rating of performances leaning towards satisfactory level.
 6. In as much as the findings reveal, future researchers may investigate further the problems met while performing their roles as school head and classroom teacher and correlate their performance to other factors.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

Anonymity, consent, and beneficence are the three research ethics that were upheld in this study. Data privacy was given the highest concern during the research process to guarantee that the data were securely collected. The research did not reveal any personal data that the participants submitted. Furthermore, copies of the consent form were given to the teachers who supplied the student data, making sure the teachers-in-charge knew about their involvement. The researcher guaranteed that the information would be handled with the highest confidentiality and went into detail about the procedure for collecting it. Additionally, if they felt it was necessary, the TICs had the choice to not participate at all. The researcher concluded by telling the respondents that there would be no advantages.

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